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Novel LED-based radiation source and its application in diffuse reflectometry and polarization measurements

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Abstract. An LED sphere radiator (LED-SR) was constructed to improve the accuracy in spectral radiance factor measurements performed with the robot-based gonireflectometer at PTB. Its properties with respect to the spectral range and coverage, the temporal stability, and the homogeneity of the radiation field are presented. Two types of matte ceramic reflection standards were used for spectral radiance factor validation measurements comparing the standardly used halogen sphere radiator (Halogen-SR) and the LED-SR. Due to its designed spectral range at the border between the visible and the UV-A spectral range, the LED-SR is well suited for many applications in diffuse reflectometry. Its use for absolute radiance factor measurements and investigations of the fluorescence properties of diffuse reflecting samples is shown. Reliable polarization-resolved measurements at wavelengths below 430 nm could be carried out with PTB's gonireflectometer for the first time due to the beneficial signal-to-noise ratio of the LED-SR.

1. Motivation

The gonireflectometer of PTB [1] uses a Halogen-SR as standard radiation source in the VIS and near-infrared spectral range. It is a barium sulfate coated sphere radiator with a 400 W quartz-tungsten halogen lamp [2], which is an easy-to-operate and reliable light source producing a spatially homogeneous and unpolarized irradiation. However, it has the limitation that the available radiance and stability quickly decrease towards UVA, where various materials exhibit higher absorption.

Thus, we developed a new sphere radiator, which uses light-emitting diodes (LEDs) as radiation source, covering wavelengths from about 360 nm to 430 nm. It generates a much higher sample irradiance compared with the Halogen-SR and considerably improves the signal quality and stability at short wavelengths. The newly developed LED-SR was carefully characterized and applied in radiance factor measurements of matte ceramic samples, fluorescence estimates of these standards, and in the study of polarization effects in this spectral range.

1.1. Construction of the LED-SR

The newly developed LED-SR uses a specially designed high-power LED board as primary radiation source placed in an integrating sphere coated with sintered PTFE.

Due to its modular design LED boards for different spectral ranges can be attached to the radiator sphere. Up to now four LED boards for different spectral ranges have been designed, exemplarily covering parts of UV-B as well as the visible and the IR spectral range. Here, we focus on the board which is configured for the boundary between the visible and UV-A spectral ranges. This

board consists of 21 surface-mounted LEDs and covers the spectral range from 360 nm to 430 nm with emission peaks at 365 nm, 385 nm and 410 nm.

The LED-SR has an active temperature control system based on thermoelectrical cooling. It controls the temperature of the emitter board from the backside and guarantees a high temporal stability. In the center of the sphere an internal BaSO₄-coated reflector is mounted which serves as the emitting surface of the radiator. The specific position of the reflector inside the sphere influences the spatial and angular emission characteristics [3] and thus the accuracy of the measurement. With optimal adjustment of the longitudinal direction of the reflecting insert, a homogeneous beam profile is obtained. All individual parts of the source are described in Figure 1 [4].

Figure 1. Side view of the LED-SR with the inner reflection insert placed in its equatorial plane, sintered PTFE sphere wall coating, exchangeable high-power LED boards and its active temperature control system [4].

1.2. Characterization of the LED-SR

As main properties of the LED-SR the spectral range and coverage, the temporal stability, and the homogeneity of the radiation field are presented below.

The spectrum of the LED-SR shows a superposition of the used LEDs and exhibits a noticeably greater signal for wavelengths below 430 nm compared to the Halogen-SR (Figure 2 a).

Due to the active temperature control a temperature stability of the LED-board of ± 0.02 °C was obtained. This enabled to operate the radiator with high stability, as demonstrated by a long-term measurement of the broad-band emission of the LED-SR by using a high precision silicon photodiode. The relative detected photocurrent of the LED-SR in comparison to a comparable model of the Halogen-SR is shown in Figure 2 b. An almost linear small long-term photocurrent drift of about 0.17 % in 100 h was observed, which meets the stability requirements of the target setup.

Long-term deterioration of the sphere's coating is observed for operation times of years. The reasons depend on the specific layout of the coating, but generally the throughput of any sphere radiator is decreasing with time. Different techniques for refreshment can be applied, as e.g., re-coating of BaSO₄-surfaces or the baking out of PTFE coatings [5]. These long-term variations are too slow to have an effect in a measurement campaign of lengths of some days, nor do they influence single measurements which are performed in the scheme lamp – sample – lamp, which cancels out linear drifts.

Short term variations in the spectral composition of the radiator should be as small as possible and were investigated for the LED-SR by the comparison of the spectrum with an integration time of 120 ms measured one after the other. The deviation of the measured spectrum in the significant spectral range of the LEDs after the burn-in time was less than ± 0.2 %. The spectral deviation after 100 h compared with the initial spectrum rises only up to ± 0.5 % (Figure 2 c). To minimize effects of this short-term fluctuation, an integration time of 1 second and a 10-fold recording of each measurement point is used in the final setup. The remaining spectral fluctuation is accounted for in the standard deviation of the measurement and thus included in the statistical uncertainty.

The scanning procedure to determine the homogeneity of the radiation field of the Halogen-SR is described in detail in [2]. The optimized longitudinal position of the reflection insert close to the equatorial plane is decisive for the homogeneity setting of the sphere radiators (Figure 1). For the LED-SR a final homogeneity of the radiation field of about $\pm 0.3\%$ was achieved, which is comparable to the one of the Halogen-SR stated in [2, 4] (Figure 2 d).

Figure 2. a) Relative spectral irradiance of the LED-SR (blue) and Halogen-SR (black). b) Relative detected long-term photocurrent of LED-SR and Halogen-SR. c) Spectral Stability of the LED-SR. d) Two-dimensional homogeneity plot of the emitted radiance of the LED-SR and Halogen-SR normalized to the center value [2, 4].

2. Application of the LED-SR

2.1. Spectral Radiance Factor Measurement

Using the LED-SR and the Halogen-SR, absolute spectral radiance factors $\beta(\lambda)$ of a white and red ceramic were determined with an angle of incidence $\theta_i = 45^\circ$ and an angle of detection $\theta_t = 0^\circ$. Seven repetitions were performed for each radiation source and sample and the resulting mean absolute spectral radiance factor $\beta(\lambda)$ and its attributed uncertainty with a coverage factor of $k = 1$ is shown in Figure 3. The determined values agree well with each other within their uncertainty range. A small divergence of the curves for the white sample below 385 nm may be attributed to increasing noise-floor of the Halogen-SR measurements.

The total measurement uncertainty of the spectral radiance factor was determined by considering various systematic and statistical effects. For both samples the measurement uncertainty is smaller for the LED-SR. The higher radiant power and the good stability of the LED-SR result in a smaller statistical uncertainty, which turns out to be the largest uncertainty component in the observed spectral range.

The systematic uncertainty contributions for both sources can be considered basically the same, except the spectral bandwidth-related uncertainty which has a much larger impact for LED-SR than for Halogen-SR due to its structured spectrum. Even taking this contribution into account the LED-SR still shows a smaller overall uncertainty in its design wavelength range from 360 nm to 430 nm [6]. This is underlined by the results for the low-reflective red sample, which shows only a slightly higher uncertainty than for the white standard when measured with the LED-SR.

It is therefore shown that the application of the LED-SR results in a considerable improvement with respect to the achievable measurement uncertainty.

Figure 3. a) Measured absolute spectral radiance factor $\beta(\lambda)$ ($k = 1$) of a white and red matte ceramic sample with the LED-SR and Halogen-SR in $45^\circ:0^\circ$ geometry. b) The measured spectral radiance factor difference $\beta_{\text{LED-SR}} - \beta_{\text{Halogen-SR}}$ for the white and red ceramic sample obtained by using both radiation sources.

2.2. Fluorescence Effects

Some reflectance standards, e.g. matte ceramic samples, exhibit a small, but measurable amount of fluorescence emitted in bands from 500 nm to 600 nm and 630 nm to 850 nm when illuminated with wavelengths below 450 nm [7]. This is shown in Figure 4 qualitatively by illuminating two sample types either by broad band white light or by a so-called black-light mercury radiation and capturing the emission by a commercial CCD-camera. The predominantly green fluorescence of the ceramic sample, whereas sintered PTFE shows no effect, is resulting by the excitation wavelength of the source and the reduced red sensitivity of the camera.

Figure 4. PTFE standard (left) and ceramic sample (right) under white light (1,3) and UV lamp 365 nm (2,4) irradiation.

To generate a more detailed information on fluorescence effects, the LED-SR is well suited because it delivers a high output in that spectral range, that is relevant to produce fluorescence in sensitive samples. Although in principle also the Halogen-SR generates fluorescence, the use of the LED-SR is advantageous because it does not emit at wavelengths above about 450 nm and all reflected radiation in this range must stem from the sample. To determine the fluorescence of the white ceramic sample a relative measurement against a sintered PTFE standard was performed. It is assumed that sintered PTFE has no fluorescent properties, so the excess of long-wavelength signal compared to the PTFE standard is attributed to fluorescence of the ceramic. Both samples were measured in $45^\circ/0^\circ$ -geometry consecutively and their reflectance recorded with a CCD detector equipped spectrometer [8].

The measured spectra were corrected for the spectral response function and normalized to the most prominent excitation wavelength. The observed signal difference between PTFE and the ceramic sample in the spectral range above 450 nm is attributed to sample fluorescence. Thus, the fluorescence was calculated by subtracting the corrected and normalized PTFE spectrum from the ceramic sample as shown by the spectrum in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Relative fluorescence of a matte ceramic sample determined against a sintered PTFE standard and using the LED-SR as radiation source.

The observed fluorescence spectrum agrees well with the findings of [7], also clearly depicting the red emission. The resulting spectrum shown here is stemming from broad-band excitation by the LED-SR. Spectrally resolved results and fluorescence influence on the absolute radiance factor will be outlined in detail in [6].

2.3. Polarization studies

Previous studies in the VIS spectral range have shown that polarization can have a large influence in reflectometry, even for quasi-Lambertian samples like ceramics [9]. The LED-SR now opens up the possibility to conduct similar studies in the VIS-to-UVA spectral range, which was not possible before in reasonable measuring time due to the low signal level of the Halogen-SR in this range.

To determine the polarization properties of the LED-SR itself, its Stokes parameters have been determined, the result is shown in Figure 6. It can be considered to be randomly polarized since all Stokes parameters are equal to zero within their attributed uncertainty with a coverage factor $k = 2$.

Figure 6. Stokes parameters of the LED-SR. Since values all are equal to zero, the LED-SR can be considered randomly polarized.

Previous studies in the VIS showed that the blue ceramic sample exhibits the largest polarization dependence for differently colored ceramics, so results for this blue ceramic are shown here. It was observed that for in-plane geometries, only the principle-axes-related linear polarization component $M_0 \neq 0$, so it is sufficient to consider β for s- and p-polarization, i.e. β_s and β_p and their ratio $\beta_{\text{ratio}} = \beta_s / \beta_p$.

To study the influence of geometry, β has been determined with either $\theta_i = 0^\circ$ and variable θ_r (-60° to 60° in steps of 15°) or vice versa. These measurements have been conducted at several different wavelengths in the VIS-to-UVA range. Results are shown in Figure 7. It can be observed that the polarization effects are more pronounced at larger θ_i . Since $M_0 < 0$, the reflected light is predominantly s-polarized. These findings are consistent with what has been observed in the long-range part of the VIS spectral range. For variable θ_r , a similar behavior was observed.

The relation between the degree of polarization (DOP) and the total reflectivity is shown in Figure 8, left panel. Data acquired with the LED-SR (365 nm, 400 nm, 425 nm) as well as with the Halogen-SR (700 nm and 750 nm) are shown. It can be seen that the lower the total reflectivity, the higher the DOP. This applies in the entire VIS-to-UVA and VIS range. For variable θ_i the DOP is slightly larger than for the reverse geometry.

The observed reflectance data have been modelled using a microfacet-based model [10], see right panel of Figure 8. The fitting parameters are the refractive index n , the surface roughness σ_0 , the correlation length τ and an unpolarized reflectivity $f_{\text{BRDF, ud}}$. It can be seen that $f_{\text{BRDF, ud}}$ is the only parameter that varies significantly with wavelength. This is due to a wavelength-dependent penetration behaviour. This leads to a different contribution of bulk scattering to the reflected light which is unpolarized compared to the more Fresnel-type surface reflection.

Figure 7. Stokes parameter M_0 and radiance factor ratio for variable angle of incidence, determined at three wavelengths in the VIS-to-UVA range.

Figure 8. Relation between DOP and total reflectivity (left panel). The lower the total reflectivity, the larger the DOP. Result of modelling with microfacet-based model (right panel).

3. Conclusion

A newly developed LED sphere radiation source equipped with a high-power LED board and an active temperature regulation was developed. The basic properties such as spectral range, temporal stability and homogeneity of the radiation field were characterized and fulfill the necessary requirements for applying this radiation source at the gonioreflectometer to determine the spectral radiance factor. Validation measurements show that achievable measurement uncertainties in the spectral range between 360 nm and 430 nm can be reduced significantly. Due to the beneficial signal-to-noise ratio of the LED-SR it could be successfully applied for other applications like fluorescence determination of diffuse reflecting samples and polarization-resolved measurements. The results demonstrate that the LED-SR is an appropriate radiation source for spectral radiance factor measurements at the border between visible and UV-A wavelengths and due to this spectral range, it is also well suited for many other applications in diffuse reflectometry measurements.

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